

STRATEGIC PHILANTHROPY AND MARKETING PERFORMANCE OF SELECTED DEPOSIT MONEY BANKS IN AKWA IBOM STATE: THE MODERATING ROLE OF THE OPERATIONAL BUSINESS ENVIRONMENT

Affiah, Eno Aniefiok, Ibok, Nkanikpo Ibok and Aniefiok Okon Akpan

Department of Marketing Akwa Ibom State University, Obio Akpa Campus.

Email: affiahenol@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10878550>

Abstract: The study examined the moderating role of the business operational environment on the relationship between strategic philanthropy and marketing performance. This study was premised on the inconsistent conclusion of many studies carried out on the influences of strategic philanthropy on marketing performance. The study, which is hinged on the stakeholder's theory adopted the questionnaire as data collection instrument and survey research design was used. The study population consisted of employees of five Deposit money banks in Uyo metropolis, namely: Zenith Bank PLC, Guaranty Trust Bank, First Bank, United bank for Africa and Ecobank PLC. Purposive sampling technique was adopted while the Krejcie and Morgan's sample size determination table was used to determine the sample size of two hundred and fifty two (252) respondents. The data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics (Regression, models). Findings revealed that the perceptual factors of strategic philanthropy (inclusion, transparency and collaboration) had significant effect on marketing performance of Deposit Money Banks in Uyo Metropolis. The result further revealed that the operational business environment play a positive and significant moderating role on the relationship between strategic philanthropy and marketing performance of Deposit money banks in Uyo metropolis. Hence, we recommended that; the process of determination and adoption of philanthropic engagements should be inclusive & transparent. Corporations should work with non-profit organization to effect the desired social change. Popular crowd funding platforms like Go-fund-me, kickstarter, 234 giveaway is a can be used to get others involved in the drive for social change and stakeholders should be adequately informed about firm's philanthropic activities in order to achieve a positive outcome.

Keywords: Strategic Philanthropy, Marketing performance, operational business environment.

INTRODUCTION

Today's socio-economic landscape is shaped by two major forces: Technology and globalization. In response to globalization, consumers expect organizations to provide solutions that will make the global world a better place for people to live in. The move by organizations to make the world a better place has led to increased involvement in activities such as charitable giving, community service programmes, environment friendly practices and various quality of life efforts. In regards to charitable giving, organizations may strive to align such intentions with the hearts of their employees and consumers while quality of life issues may revolve around programmes such as: training for the hard core unemployed, sponsoring clean-up programme provision of primary education, primary healthcare etc. Corporate Philanthropy represents modern engagements by proactive firms to promote human wellbeing or goodwill. Porter and Kramer (2011) hints that philanthropy is often used as a form of public relations or advertising to promote a company's image through investment in cause-related activities or high-profile sponsorship. Kramer & Porter (2014) further explained that it is hard to determine the benefits a company gets from involvement in philanthropy. This may however implies that the connection between an organization good actions and customer attitudes is so indirect that is impossible to measure.

Corporate philanthropy has become an inevitable part of the business world not only as a result of globalization but also due to increased shareholders expectations. Freeman *et al.*, (2010) advocates for the inclusion of stakeholders in the pursuant and practice of corporate philanthropy. The stakeholder's theory which provides the theoretical basis for philanthropy behavior requires management to look beyond the internal interest of the firm and also consider the interest of all stakeholders affected by firm's decision when making important operational and strategic decision. Such inclusion will result in increased shareholders satisfaction propelled by the achievement of sustainable profit gained through improved brands, employees and customers satisfaction (Freeman *et al.*, 2010). Luring and Thomson (2010) discussed two categories of stakeholders but however implored that preference should be given to those with legitimate interest in the firm such as owners, employees, and customers before consideration is paid to competitors, supplies and the local society.

Corporate philanthropy has become desirable because stakeholders now expect companies to be more accountable and transparent while some organization may handle their philanthropic programs internally, some delegate such management to non-profit organizations or the local community organizations. Institutional philanthropy is influenced and shaped by socio-economic, culture and political factors. Inyang (2020) revealed that the practice corporate philanthropy in Nigeria has been predominately shaped by the West and its origin is traceable to the multi-nationals companies (MNCs) operating within the oil sector. Although, there's a presumption that CSR-related practices are largely homogenous, Amaeshi, *et al.*, (2006) indicated that it is a socio-economic embedded construct. This suggests that firms are products of the socio-economic environment in which they operate in and this largely shapes or influence their philanthropic engagement.

Adidu and Clanye (2006) assents this argument by showing that a company's strategy should be in tandem with the framework of forces which constitute the business environment to be successfully, Santoso, Purwoko, Umar

and Renwarin (2020) showed that the external and internal environment exert a significant influence and recommended that organization should align their business strategy with the environment.

A cursory look at the economies of most developing countries indicates features such as political instability, government inefficiency, low standard of living, low level of economic wealth and high level of corruption (Ibok, 2023) Nigeria is a good example of such country faced with poverty, civil unrest, insecurity, poor infrastructural development which has disturbed the business environment and in turn business performance. This explains why the focus of most philanthropic engagements by Deposit money banks is in the area of health, education, humanitarian relief, empowerment and poverty reduction. These modes of participation are conceived to cover instances of government administration disappointments and to ensure their business advantage. Although, technology has change the way the financial sector operates, especially with the rise of online and mobile banking Cai, Xu & Yang (2021) confirmed that the local environment is still important given both anecdotal and empirical evidence that consumers still prefer local banks. Extent literature shows that consumers prefer firms that support local cause in the environment they operate (Abrams, 2019).

Recent research has shown a shift from corporate philanthropy strategic philanthropy. This new line of thought encourage corporations to play a leadership role in solving social problems by finding initiatives that will make a world a better place while improving the firm's strategic position. Strategic philanthropy specifically links philanthropic engagements to corporate objectives. With data depicting donations made by Deposit money banks and other firms to the coalition against COVID-19 (CACOVID) and other quality of life programmes in Nigeria (Bande 2022).

The question raised by the study is: Does this strategic giving influence the marketing performance of the Deposit money banks? What role does the operational business environment play in the moderating the relationship between strategic philanthropy and the marketing performance of selected deposit money banks (DMBs) in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State.

Statement of the Problem

Strategic philanthropy which is one of the wide spread form of corporate social responsibility (CSR) (Carroll, 1991) is considered by many as a concept of charity only. This misconception has distorted its value contribution to organizational performance. Hence it becomes imperative to evaluate its the effect on marketing activities. Strategic corporate philanthropy has been linked to enhanced competitive advantage, (Porter & Kramer, 2011) reputational capital, increased sales, (Kotler & Lee, 2005) improved organizational performance (Balogun, Aina & Olateju, 2022) but Sameer, (2021), Madugba, Okafor & Kesto (2017) disagree that corporate philanthropy influenced organizational performance positively. This gray area of inconclusiveness motivates the need to conduct a study on this topic.

More so, it's been observed that most corporations are unable to take advantage of the opportunities engagement in strategic corporate philanthropy offers an organization due to poor disclosure practices, non-inclusion of stakeholders and poor collaboration in the adoption and implementation of philanthropy

engagements. Also, most philanthropy engagements by corporate firms are not only sporadic but inconsistent thereby making it difficult to determine the effect on marketing performance.

Furthermore, research suggests that a company's competitive strategy should be in tandem with the framework of forces which constitute the operational business environment to be successful. (Abang , Olalekan, Mukaila & Umaru (2021) carried out an extensive empirical review of 302 peer reviewed published between 2011 – 2020 and found that only 42 articles representing 13.70% of the reviewed articles on business environment considered the operational business environment as study focus. This however indicates a gap in knowledge that should be filled with future studies. This study aims to fill this gap by examining the moderating role of the operational business environment on the relationship between strategic philanthropy and marketing performance.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to examine the influence of strategic philanthropy on marketing performance of deposit money bank moderated by the operational business environment the specific objectives are:

- ❖ To examine the effect of perceptual factors of strategic philanthropy (inclusion, Transparency and collaboration) on marketing performance of selected deposit money banks in Uyo metropolis Akwa Ibom State.
- ❖ To examine the role of the business operational environment in moderating the relationship between strategic philanthropy and marketing performance.

Research Hypotheses

The following Null Hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

- ❖ The perceptual factors of strategic philanthropy (inclusion, Transparency and collaboration) have no significant effect on marketing performance.
- ❖ The operational business environment does not significantly moderate the relationship between strategic philanthropy and marketing performance

LITERATURE REVIEW

Strategic Philanthropy

Philanthropic activities represent modern engagement by proactive firms in promoting human well-being or goodwill of firms. Organization use such as efforts to improve their competitive stance and the quality of the business environment in which they operate in. Watick and Woods (1998) cited in Ricks (2002) describes philanthropy as a discretionary responsibility of a firm involving decisions on how to voluntarily allocate its slack resources to charitable or social service for which there are clear expectations on how the firms should perform.

Corporate philanthropy can be undertaken as:-

- Altruism-giving in the interest of others without self-interest
- Shared benefits –giving to the common good with general but not specific benefit

- Enlightened self interest – the chance to enhance a product or service where the donor looks for specific benefit in the long term.
- Charitable investment – an expectation of short term gain greater than what is invested.
- Stewardship – a direct focus on maximizing shareholders wealth.

Research indicates a shift from corporate philanthropy to strategic giving. Strategic corporate philanthropy empowers an organization to use its philanthropic activities to meet marketing and other business related objectives. Strategic corporate philanthropy explicitly links philanthropic engagements by an organization to a corporate objective which according to Varadarajan & Menon (1998) may include:- customer pacification, facilitation of market entry, thwarting negative publicity, increased sales and more. Kotler & Lee (2005) linked strategic philanthropy to increased customers' loyalty and firms' pride. Tilson (2005) observed that cause – related marketing evolved from this strategic view of philanthropy.

Strategic corporate philanthropy comes in firms beyond and inclusive of monetary gifts. Inyang (2020) observed that it may take the form of cash donations, scholarship, donations of products/services, provision of technical expertise, allowing the use of facilities and distribution channels etc. Other forms of strategic philanthropy include: sponsorship of local and national events, Arts and Cultural programs sponsorship, mentorship, employee & employer involvement (voluntary services) provision of education and primary health care facilities, executive loan and many more. Philanthropy giving varies from one company to the other and also from one country to the other. While large firms differ in their approach to philanthropy by depicting their social credentials, smaller firms focus more on developing reliant relationships with their primary stakeholders.(Baden, 2010)

The concept of philanthropy is at variance with traditional economic reasoning which posit that wealth maximization of shareholders should be the only consideration of managers (firms) Friedman (2002) referred to such actions as the “levy of illegal tax” and contend that whereas human beings have a moral responsibility for their activities companies are not human beings but legal entities therefore social issues and problems should be the sole responsibility of the state. Accordingly, if stakeholders wish to support a charitable cause then they should so as individuals. Despite the contentions against corporate giving, some researchers agree that acts of goodwill somehow pay off (Adegbola; 2014; Kule et al; 2018 Kotler & Lee; 2005)

Perceptual Factors of Strategic Philanthropy

Factors contributing to customer's perception of what constitute philanthropy are referred to as perceptual factors of philanthropy. Research conducted by Han |(2021) showed transparency, sustainability, authenticity, value congruence, collaboration, corporate ethics and corporate reputation as the main perceptual factors of corporate philanthropy While Hawn & Ioannou (2006) emphasized on the multi dimensionality of stakeholders and their diverging influence on firm's performance as important perceptual factors affecting the practice of philanthropy. More so, Se-Hyeon (2022) emphasized on sustainability, authenticity, value congruence and transparency.

Building from stakeholders' theory, the study operationalize that firms will benefit more from strategic philanthropic (SP) activities when stakeholders perceive such efforts as genuine and information relating to such efforts are available and accessible to them and the process of determination is inclusive and transparent with due consideration to the firm's operational environment.

An effective strategic philanthropic engagement should begin with stakeholder inclusion, but it should be noted that culture of inclusion does not happen by chance. Corporations should be structured to enhance inclusivity among stakeholders. This may entails holding diverse meeting with every divigent group to determine social issues or causes to address. Corporation can engage in dialogue with stakeholders in connection with selection and implementation of philanthropy engagement and achieve voluntary agreement to tackle internal and expectations (Lauring & Thomson, 2010) Inclusion helps to foster agreement. If stakeholders are united by the mission, vision and values each can play their role in serving the corporation's interest in a complementary way. Transparency is crucial to fix credibility: (Adkins, 2014) When philanthropy engagements are not transparent, stakeholders may feel like they are "giving in the dark". Not sharing information makes it difficult to know the impact the organization is making. Hence, Transparency help corporations to prove to employees, investors, consumers and the immediate community as well as the wider world that they are committed to making a change while securing competitive advantage.

Another essential ingredient in the success equation of corporations is collaboration. Collaboration help corporation by giving them more than just funds or resources, it enables them to create an actionable plan that will maximize their social impact. When non-profit organization and corporations (donors) collaborate both learn and benefit from the partnership. Strategic funding options for collaborative philanthropy include: grants, sponsorship, crowd funding programs, impact investors etc. The greatest benefit derivable for corporations partnering with non-profit organization is increase morale and employee engagement (Eikenberry & Breeze, 2016) Partnership can also increase brand loyalty since customers will feel like they are supporting a noble cause.

Marketing Performance

Literature has somewhat failed to unearth a clear and explicit definition of the term "Marketing Performance" even though research on it is well established. Early work on measurement of marketing performance focused in the financial measures of profit, sales and cash flow (Bonoma & Clark, 1988). But new non-financial measures of output, such as customer satisfaction, customer loyalty and brand equity have attracted considerable research interest. Levent and Kosan (2013) indicated that the non financial measures of marketing performance are market share, customer satisfaction, brand equity and innovation while the financial measures include: sales analysis, market share analysis, the ratio of marketing sales expenditure to sales.

Nwokah and Didia (2015) employed sales growth, customer retention, return on investment, market share, employees motivation as proxies of marketing performance. Ambler (2000) point out the lack of precision in the terminology used to define marketing performance and proposed the adoption of the word "metric" to capture a top-level measure of marketing performance.

Accordingly, the marketing science institute (2004) defines marketing metrics as the performance indicators top management used to track and assess progress specially the marketing performance of a business or business unit.

Operational Business Environment

The business environment represents the totality of the factors that affects, influence or determine the operations or performance of a firm. It determines what is possible for the business firm to achieve within a given time period. Owing its strategic role of determining organizational success or performance constant monitoring and evaluation becomes imperative to spot the opportunities and limitations inherent in the firm's operational environment.

The term "business environment" covers both specific and general forces. Whereas the general forces cover dimensions such as political, social, legal and technological conditions the specific forces otherwise referred to as the competitive or operational forces cover dimensions such as laws and regulations, political influence, infrastructure, competition, employees issues, consumers and community issues.

The operational environment exerts considerable influence in business performance and it is a major determinant of business strategy to be adopted by corporations (Ganguli, 2019). Luo & Zhao (2015) indicated that the operational business environment is responsible for the high mortality rate and poor performance of most businesses. The Authors Aver that factors that make up the operational environment are political, economic, social, information, infrastructure, physical environment and time. Although there are differences in conceptualization, consensus exists in dimension such as political, infrastructure, physical environment and the economic dimensions.

Empirical Review

Kayirangwa, Namusonge & Kule (2018) conducted a study on the influence of philanthropic corporate social responsibility strategy (PCSR) on perceived firm performance in the Telecommunication sector in Rwanda, Kenya. They adopted both the qualitative and quantitative research design and collected data from a sample of One Hundred and Forty-Five (145) respondents using Taro Yamane formula from a population of two hundred and twenty eight (228) managers and CSR related staff of selected telecommunication firms in Rwanda. Regression and correlation coefficient were used to analyze the relationship between philanthropic marketing and the performance of telecommunications firms. Results showed that involvement in CSR helps to improve perceived firm performance.

Maignan, Ferrel & Ferrel (2005) analyzed the stakeholder's model for implementing social responsibility in marketing. The study adopted a qualitative approach to research and put-forth an Eight –step model for implementing CSR in corporations to include: discovering organizational norms and values, identifying stakeholders, identifying stakeholder's issues, assessing the meaning of CSR, audit current practices implementing CSR initiatives and gaining stakeholders feedback. The study concluded that the stakeholders methodology presented by the authors is the main logic underpinning the sound implementation of CSR.

To further clarify on the concept of CSR, Arco-castro, Lopez perez, Gomez & Garde Sanchez (2020) carried out a study to determine if stakeholders modulate philanthropy strategy. The study which was carried out in 13 European countries in 2018 focused on 221 companies, Authors utilized data from sustainability database, a data provider for socially responsible investors. Regression model and correlation co-efficient were used to analyze the secondary data. Findings showed that a positive relationship exist between corporate philanthropy activities managed through foundations and company cohesion with employees and recommend that management of corporations should take into account the stakeholders requirements and stakeholders should show greater affinity and trust with the corporation for philanthropy channeled through foundations.

Hwang, Kim & lee (2020) investigated the importance of philanthropic corporate social responsibility (PCSR) and its impact on attitude and behavioral intentions with focus on Barista disability status. In the study, the quantitative approach was used to examine the hypotheses and data collected from two types of Starbucks: disable baristas providing services and non-disabled baristas providing services. Thus data was generated from five hundred and seventy –seven (577) respondents consisting of customers while descriptive statistics and factor analysis was used to analyze the data. The results of data analysis showed that philanthropic corporate social responsibility positively affect attitude which in turn has a positive influence on intentions to use, word – of – mouth intentions and willingness to pay more. Based on the findings the study recommends the hiring of people with disabilities.

Se-Hyeon (2023) carried out a study to verify how the factors contributing to consumers perceptions of corporate Philanthropy affect brand equity and consumer loyalty mediated by consumer-company identification and trust. With data collected through online survey from 390 respondents analyzed using SPSS Software. The results showed that the effects of factors contributing to consumers perceptions of corporate philanthropy on consumer loyalty through consumer- company identification, consumer trust and brand equity were statistically significant. Consumer perception of transparency has a significant indirect effect on consumer trust mediated by consumer-company identification. The study recommended that corporate philanthropy must be considered at a more strategic level in order to maintain consistency of values and set goals and plans that are not short term.

Abdullah & Mansor (2018) investigated the moderating effect of the business environment on the relationship between entrepreneurial skills and business performance of small business in Iraq, Baghdad. The study adopted the survey design and 300 respondents were selected to represent the study population using Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) table for sample size determination. Study finding indicated that the business environment moderates the relationship between entrepreneurial skills and small business performance.

METHODOLOGY

A cross sectional survey of the population was adopted for the study due to the heterogeneous of nature of the study elements. The study population consisted of eight hundred and fifty (850) employees of selected banks in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State.

Table 1: List of Selected Banks

S/N	Names of Banks	Numbers of Employees
1	Zenith Bank	206
2	GT Bank	89
3	First Bank	245
4	UBA	220
5	Ecobank	90
	TOTAL	850

A sample size of 265 respondents was determined using the Krejcie and Morgan table (1970). The sample selection is depicted below.

Table 2: Sample Selection Table

S/N	Names of Banks	Number of Respondents
1	Zenith Bank	60
2	GT Bank	30
3	First Bank	72
4	UBA	68
5	Ecobank	35
	Total	265

The purposive sampling technique which is a non-probability sampling technique was used to collect data from respondents. The sampling technique was adopted because it makes it possible for researchers to select respondents who can provide information for systematic inquiry. Hence respondents used for the study include:

- i. Educated employees (at least to a diploma level)
- ii. Those that have been with the organization for at least two years.
- iii. Those that are available and accessible

The research instrument was administered to the respondents with the help of Human Resource manager (HR) of the adopted banks. Participants were duly informed of the purpose of the research and the significance of the study. From the two hundred and sixty five (265) administered questionnaire copies, only 252 copies were properly filled and retrieved by the researcher, implying that thirteen (13) copies of the questionnaire were considered invalid. Hence, (252) respondents became the validated sample size of the study.

The survey instrument developed by the researcher to elicit response was in two parts. Section-A elicited responses concerning gender, educational qualification, age, employment status and years of experience. The second part comprised of 22 items related to strategic philanthropy and marketing performance. The items on the questionnaire were measured on a five-point-likert scale.

Data collected from the questionnaire was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Specifically, frequency tables percentages was used to analyze the demographic data, while multiple regression and Hierarchical regression model was used in testing the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Demographic profile of the respondents

The demographic profile of the respondents are presented in Table 3

Table 3 Demographic profile of the respondents

Variable	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	105	41.7
	Female	147	58.3
	Total	252	100
	Educational qual.		
	SSCE/WASSCE	-	-
	Diploma/NCE	74	29.3
	B.Sc./ HND	141	56.0
	Postgraduate degree	37	14.7
	Others	-	-
	Total	252	100
Age distribution	20 – 25years	60	23.8
	26 – 35years	108	42.9
	36 – 45years	55	21.8
	46 – 55years	27	10.7
	56years and above	2	0.8
	Total	252	100
Employment Status	Professional staff	177	70.2
	Unprofessional staff	75	29.8
	Total	252	100
Years of experience	Below 2 years	-	-
	2 – 4 years	69	27.4
	5 – 7 years	104	41.3
	8years and above	79	31.3
	Total	252	100

The demographic profile of the respondents were addressed Table 3. From the result, 58.3% of the respondents were females as against 41.7% who were males. From the result ridge, the researcher was not biased, although equal opportunity was given to both male and female staff in studied DMBs to contribute but, the disparity was based on the number of male and female staff employed in the banking sector. The little variation in gender is because the population of employees in the banking sector is more of women as against the male counterpart, because women have the persuasive capacity to dialogue with existing customer's compliant using empathetic strategy and scouting capability for prospective customers (Ziad et al, 2012).

Tables 3 further revealed that, 56.0% of the respondents were B.Sc/HND holders; followed by Diploma/NCE holders constituting 29.3% of the respondents. The postgraduate degree holders constituted 14.7% of the sample. However, none of the respondents had SSCE/WASSCE as their highest academic qualification. The educational qualification of the respondents appeared impressive as majority had formal education. This could imply that the bank staff in the study area are enlightened, learned, informed and receptive to philanthropic marketing.

As shown in Table 3 above, 42.9% of the respondents were within 26 – 35 years of age. This was followed by 23.8% and 21.8% of the respondents who were between 20 – 25years of age and 36 - 45 years of age respectively. The least were 0.8% of the respondents was above 55 years of age. From the result, most of the respondents were young, vibrant and energetic people who are ready to work for the common goal of the bank. From the result, more than 85% of the employees are below 45 years of age which is in consonance with the fact that, most of the banking firms in Nigeria employ fresh graduates who are below the age of 27years in most cases. From the above categorization, most of the respondents (25 -45 years) fell within the active working class, which implies that those in this age group are up and doing. They can make rational decisions pertaining to philanthropic marketing and its implications on marketing performance of banking firms in the study area.

As shown from the employment status, 70.2% of the respondents are professional staff while 29.8% are not professional staff. The high rate of professional staff is based on the routine that every worker needs to belong to a professional body to symbolize expertise.

From the results in Table 3, majority of the respondents (41.3%) have 5 – 7 years of banking services experience, followed by 69 (27.4%) and 79 (31.3%) of the staff with 2-4 years and above 8years of working experience in the banking sector respectively. However, none of the respondent had less than 2years working experience in the banking sector. This imply that the sampled respondents have spent a good number of years with the bank; and might have been involved in series of philanthropic marketing related activities and evaluate their implications on marketing performance.

TEST OF HYPOTHESES

Test of Hypothesis 1: H_{01} : The perceptual factors of strategic Philanthropy (inclusion, transparency and collaboration) have no significant effect on marketing performance

Table 4: Multiple linear regression analysis result on influence of perceptual factors of strategic philanthropy on marketing performance of money deposit bank

Variables	Parameters	Coefficient	Std error	Tcal – Value
Constant	β_0	1.586	0.273	5.813***
Inclusive philanthropy (X ₁)	β_1	0.062	0.026	2.352**
Transparency philanthropy (X ₂)	β_2	0.536	0.049	10.941***
Collaboration philanthropy (X ₃)	β_3	0.048	0.021	2.286**
R-Square (R²)		0.567		
Adjusted R – Square (R²)		0.532		
F – Statistics Value		40.396		
F – Probability value		0.000		
Durbin-Watson stat.		1.985		

Decision Rule: If $F_{cal} > F_{tab}$ accept the alternate and reject Null hypothesis. Otherwise accept the null hypothesis. (***) = 1%), (** = 5%), and (* = 10%) denotes significance of coefficient at level respectively; t-tab value = 1.972, df = 248, Dependent Variable: marketingperf, Predictors: (Constant), Collaboration, inclusive, transparency

Source: Field Survey, 2023 (SPSS Version 22 computation)

The coefficient of inclusive philanthropy (X₁) was statistically significant and positively related to marketing performance of deposit money bank at 5 percent probability level. This implies that in unit increase in inclusive philanthropic activity leads to 0.062unit increase in marketing performance of deposit money. From the result, inclusive philanthropy has a t-cal value of 2.352 which is greater than 1.972 tabulated value at 0.05 degree of freedom. In effect, since the t-calculated value is greater than the t-tabulated value in absolute terms, the researcher rejected null hypothesis in favour of alternate hypothesis stating that, inclusive Philanthropy has significant influence on marketing performance of money deposit banks in the study area.

The estimated value of transparency philanthropy (X₂) was statistically significant and positively related to marketing performance of money deposit bank at 1 percent probability level. This signifies that in unit increase in transparent philanthropy leads to 0.536unit increase in marketing performance of deposit money. The result also indicated that, transparency philanthropy has a t-cal value of 10.941 which is greater than 1.972 tabulated value at 0.05 degree of freedom. In effect, since the t-calculated value is greater than the t-tabulated value in absolute terms, the researcher rejected null hypothesis in favour of alternate hypothesis stating that, transparency philanthropy has significant effect on marketing performance of money deposit bank.

Collaborative philanthropy (X₃) was statistically significant and positively related to marketing performance of money deposit banks at 5 percent level. The coefficient of collaborative philanthropy (X₃) of 0.048, revealed that, a unit increase in collaborative philanthropy, holding other variables constant, will lead to increase in

marketing performance of money deposit banks by 0.048 units. From the result, since the collaborative philanthropy has a t-cal value of 2.286 which is greater than 1.972 tabulated value at 0.05 degree of freedom. Thus, marketing performance of money deposit banks will increase by 0.048units, if the studied banking firms increase their collaborative philanthropy by a units in the study area.

The coefficient of multiple determination (R^2) was 0.567, which implies that 56.7% changes in the dependent variable was explained by changes in the independent variable, while 56.7% was unexplained by stochastic terms in the model. Thus, the independent variable (inclusive, transparency and collaboration philanthropy) can only explain 56.7 percent of changes in marketing performance of money deposit banks, leaving 43.3% unexplained. The R^2 adjusted was 53.2% indicating a goodness of fit of the regression model adopted in this study which is statistically significant at 5% probability level. The Durbin-Watson statistical value of 1.985 was observed which falls within 1.8 to 2.5, implying that there is no evidence of autocorrelation in the data analysis. More so, the f-statistical (calculated) value of 40.396 was observed in the analysis which is greater than 1.972 t-table value; and f-probability value of 0.000 was observed from the analysis which is less than 0.05 (95% of freedom), indicating that estimated regression model adopted in this study is statistically significant at 5% level. With this, the researcher rejected the null hypotheses and accept alternative hypothesis hence, the perceptual factors of strategic philanthropy (inclusion, transparency and collaboration) have significant effect on marketing performance of deposit money banks.

Test of hypothesis 2

Ho₂, The operational business environment does not significantly moderate the relationship between strategic philanthropy and marketing performance. In order to test the hypothesis, three variables were identified as follows:

- (i) marketing performance as dependent variable.
- (ii) strategic philanthropy as independent variable.
- (iii) operational business environment as moderating variables

Model summary of hierarchical regression analysis of business operational environment in moderating the relationship between strategic philanthropy and marketing performance.

Table 5 Model summary

Model Summary ^c									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.962 ^a	.925	.925	.23583	.925	3095.799	1	250	.000
2	.980 ^b	.960	.960	.17200	.035	220.983	1	249	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), strategicphilanthropy
b. Predictors: (Constant), strategicphilanthropy, operationalenvironment
c. Dependent Variable: Marketingperformance

Source: Field Survey, 2023 (SPSS Version 22 computation)

Table 6 ANOVA

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	172.175	1	172.175	3020.799	.000 ^b
	Residual	13.904	250	.056		
	Total	186.079	251			
2	Regression	178.713	2	89.356	3095.441	.000 ^c
	Residual	7.366	249	.030		
	Total	186.079	251			

a. Dependent Variable: Marketingperformance

b. Predictors: (Constant), strategicphilanthropy

c. Predictors: (Constant), strategicphilanthropy, operationalenvironment

Source: Field Survey, 2023 (SPSS Version 22 computation)

Table 7 Coefficient /estimate summary

Coefficients ^a													
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Correlations			Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error				Beta	Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Zero-order	Partial	Part	Tolerance
1	(Constant)	.286	.067		4.275	.000	.154	.417					
	Strategicphilanthropy	6.287	.113	.628	55.640	.000	6.064	6.509	.962	.962	.962	1.000	1.000
2	(Constant)	.104	.050		2.075	.039	.005	.203					
	strategicphilanthropy	3.064	.232	.694	13.211	.000	2.607	3.521	.962	.642	.167	.126	7.921
	operationalenvironment	.525	.035	.528	14.866	.000	.456	.595	.966	.686	.187	.126	7.921

a. Dependent Variable: Marketingperformance

Source: Field Survey, 2023 (SPSS Version 22 computation)

Excluded Variables ^a								
Model		Beta In	T	Sig.	Partial Correlation	Collinearity Statistics		
						Tolerance	VIF	Minimum Tolerance
1	operationalenvironment	.528 ^b	14.866	.000	.686	.126	7.921	.126
a. Dependent Variable: Marketingperformance								
b. Predictors in the Model: (Constant), strategicphilanthropy								

Table 7 Excluded variables

Source: Field Survey, 2023 (SPSS Version 22 computation)

Hierarchical regression model was used by the researcher to test hypothesis 2. The hierarchical regression is a type of regression model in which the predictors are entered in blocks. Each block represents one step (or model). In effect, the hierarchical regression model was adopted in analyzing the role of the operational business environment in moderating the relationship between strategic philanthropy and marketing performance in Table 7. The result as discovered in model summary (Model 1) revealed that, when strategic philanthropy and marketing performance are regressed against each other in the equation model, the result obtained as ($R=0.962$, $R^2=0.925$, Adjusted $R^2=0.925$, $p=0.000$ less than 0.05, $R^2\Delta=0.925$). As shown in the result, strategic philanthropy account for 92.5% variation in marketing performance. At this point, strategic philanthropy has 92.5% relationship with marketing performance of the studied banks which is extremely high. This implies that strategic philanthropy have a tangible relationship with marketing performance of the studied banks. The overall result in model one (1) (Anova Table 6) was statistically significant with the F-stat value of 3020.799 and prob. value of 0.000 less than 0.05 degree of freedom. Hence, the model is statistically significant @ 5percent probability level. Hence, strategic philanthropy operating without moderation variable has significant relationship on marketing performance of studied banks in Akwa Ibom State.

In addition, business operational environment was introduced as the moderator in the second model. And the result of the 2nd model shows business operational environment statistically moderate the relationship between strategic philanthropy and marketing performance of studied banks in Nigeria. The evidence is shown in the result of $R=0.980$, $R^2=0.960$, Adjusted $R^2=0.960$, $p=0.000 < .05$, $R^2\Delta=0.035$) shows a that the introduction of business operational environment into the model as a moderating variable and strategic philanthropy jointly account for 96.0% positive changes marketing performance of studied banks in Akwa Ibom State, as against 92.5% explained by strategic philanthropy only on marketing performance of studied banks in Akwa Ibom State. From the result, there is a significant and positive changes when business operational environment is introduced as a moderating variable in the equation. This signifies that business operational environment moderate the relationship of strategic philanthropy and marketing performance. In the same vein, model 2

(ANOVA) the F-value of 3095.441 and probability value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05 was observed from the regression analysis. This implies that the independent variable (strategic philanthropy) and the moderator (business operational environment) were statistically significant in the model adopted for the analysis. Furthermore, the standard coefficient beta value in Model 2 revealed that strategic philanthropy ($\beta = 0.628, p = 0.000$ less than 0.05) and business operational environment ($\beta = 0.694, p = 0.000 < .05$). This means a unit increase in business operational environment holding other variables constant leads to 0.694 unit increase in marketing performance of DMBs in Nigeria respectively. Adding up the effect, it shows that the increasing beta value from ($\beta = 0.628, p = 0.000$ less than 0.05) to ($\beta = 0.694, p = 0.000$ less than 0.05). Thus, the introduction of operational business environment as a moderating variable significantly moderate the relationship between strategic philanthropy and marketing performance of DMBs in Akwa Ibom State.

Discussion of Results

The study examined the influence of strategic philanthropy and marketing performance moderated by the operational business environment. The results are discussed as follows:

i. The result of the multiple regression analysis on the influence of the perceptual factors of strategic philanthropy (Inclusion, transparency and collaboration indicated that the perceptual factors have a positive and significant influence on marketing performance. Thus: the coefficient of inclusive philanthropy (X_1) was statistically significant and positively related to marketing performance of deposit money bank at 5 percent probability level. This implies that a unit increase in inclusive philanthropic activity leads to 0.062 unit increase in marketing performance of deposit money bank. The result agreed with the findings of Feroz-De-Costa (2019) who studied influence of philanthropic marketing on millennial purchase intention of sharia complaints stocks. This study suggests that philanthropic attitude has a large effect on purchase intention and brand attitude only mediates the relationship between firm generated content and purchase. Consequently Hamiton (2018) indicated that stakeholders respond favourably to philanthropic activities and their perception will be positive if they are included in the decision making process. A clear commitment to stakeholder inclusion serves as an added value for company's social responsibility programs and also creates a positive image for the company. (Wang & Qian, 2011)

The estimated value of transparency philanthropy (X_2) was statistically significant and positively related to marketing performance of deposit money banks at 1 percent probability level. This signifies that a unit increase in transparent philanthropy leads to 0.536 unit increase in the marketing performance of deposit money banks. The result affirm the findings of Lu, Liang & Wang (2020) that showed that stakeholders' perceptions and information availability across regions significantly moderate the corporate philanthropy- corporate financial performance relationship. Similarly, Hamilton (2018) confirmed that firms benefit from corporate philanthropy when their stakeholders perceive such effects as genuine and also when information on such effort is available to them. This findings is also substantiated by Mubarak, Hamed & Al Mubarak, (2019) who aver that when customer can access and verified information on the purpose of corporate activities, participation details, related cost and investment details through various channels it will positively affect the formation of strong relationship

with the companies, product and brands. Se-Hyeon (2022) showed that consumer perception of transparency has a significant indirect effect on trust mediated by consumer-company identification.

Collaborative philanthropy (X_3) was statistically significant and positively related to marketing performance of deposit money banks at 5 percent level. The coefficient of collaborative philanthropy (X_3) of 0.048, revealed that, a unit increase in collaborative philanthropy, holding other variables constant, will lead to increase in marketing performance of money deposit banks by 0.048 units. The result agrees with the findings of Hwang, Kim & Lee (2020) who investigated the importance of philanthropic corporate social responsibility (PCSR) and its impact on attitude and behavioral intentions with focus on Barista disability status. In the study, the quantitative approach was used to examine the hypotheses and data collected from two types of Starbucks: disable baristas providing services and non-disabled baristas providing services. Thus data was generated from five hundred and seventy-seven (577) respondents consisting of customers while descriptive statistics and factor analysis was used to analyze the data. The results of data analysis showed that philanthropic corporate social responsibility positively affect attitude which in turn has a positive influence on intentions to use, word-of-mouth intentions and willingness to pay more. Based on the findings the study recommends the hiring of people with disabilities. Waterford (2018) indicated that the greatest benefit derivable for corporation partnering with non-profit is increased brand loyalty because it makes customers feel like they are supporting a noble cause. Moreso, long term sustainability of cooperation is dependent on procuring the corporation of numerous constituents including but not limited to shareholders. With collaboration inspiring result can be achieved (Freeman, 1984, Thomson & Perry, 2006)

ii. The hierarchical regression analysis showed the moderating role of the operational business environment on the relationship between strategic philanthropy and marketing performance of deposit money bank. The result shows that, business operational environment plays a positive and significant moderating role in the relationship between strategic philanthropy and marketing performance of deposit money bank. The result revealed that, a conducive business environment plays a positive mediating role, in enhancing marketing performance of corporate organisation as the conducive business operational environment leads to improvement in the relationship between strategic philanthropy and marketing performance of money deposit bank of money deposit bank by 0.441. The result agrees with the findings of Abdullah & Mansor (2018) who investigated the moderating effect of the business environment on the relationship between entrepreneurial skills and business performance of small business in Iraq, Baghdad. Similarly, Marshall et al (2018) affirmed that the controversy surrounding the relationship between corporate philanthropy and corporate performance is partly due to the lack of consideration of the firm's geographical location. Liang & Renneboug (2018) averred that a firm operating environment serves as a motivator for participation in corporate philanthropy as such engagement helps to improve reputation and also attract loyal customers.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Strategic Philanthropy is a viable tool for enhancing the competitive stance of business corporations. Hence, banking firms practicing strategic philanthropy generate intangible strategic assets such as reputational capital,

sales volume, positive brand image and trust or acquiescence among regulatory institutions and legislative bodies. Although, the extent to which a firm participates in marketing philanthropy is always limited to its strategic interests, thereby ensuring that the primary objective of any business (profit maximization or the generation of shareholder wealth) is adhered to. It is therefore important for Deposit money banks to have a well thought out strategy when deciding on what services to provide to the society. In conclusion, the study showed that strategic philanthropy significantly influences marketing performance of deposit money banks.

The following recommendations were suggested on the basis of the findings of the study and the conclusion drawn

1. The process of determination and adoption of philanthropic engagements should be inclusive & transparent. Deposit money banks should work with non-profit organization to effect the desired social change. Popular crowd funding platforms like Go-fund-me, kickstarter, 234 giveaway is a good way to get others involved in the drive for social change and stakeholders should be adequately informed about the banks philanthropic activities in order to achieve a positive outcome.
2. Management of DMBs should focus more on ethical and social philanthropic activities to achieve maximum satisfaction of host communities who are also their customers, as a means to increase their sales, since the result indicates a positive relationship between peaceful coexistence and business operation.
3. Banking firms utilizing philanthropic initiatives as part of an overall market development strategy must not look for an absolute monetary return, but to a certain extent a balance of returns comprising social, and ethical transgression to the financial measures.

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